

with an authentic sample of bilobetin⁷⁻⁹ (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) revealed its identity.

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Norditerpene Dilactones, Macrophylllic Acid and Biflavones from *Podocarpus latifolius*

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BIFLAVONES¹ and norditerpene dilactones² are taxonomically associated with the genus *Podocarpus* (*Podocarpaceae*), of which norditerpene dilactones possess pronounced biological activities³. We report here the result of our investigations on *Podocarpus latifolius*.

Material used in this investigation were collected from Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, where a voucher specimen has been deposited. Air-dried stem wood (5 kg) of *P. latifolius* was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel and eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate mixtures of increasing polarity. Elution with benzene yielded a homogeneous solid which was crystallised as colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 135°; it gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard test and was identified as β -sitosterol (1). Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (17:3) afforded another solid (2) which was

Crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 235-36°. Uv spectral data indicated 2 to be aromatic and ir spectral data, indicated it to be an acid. Further, pmr spectral data showed the presence of two isopropyl and four tertiary methyl groups in 2. These facts taken together with the mass spectral data in which M^{+} appeared at m/z 630 corresponding to the composition of $C_{40}H_{54}O_6$, led to the identification of 2 as macrophylllic acid⁴. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) yielded a solid 3 which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 310-12°, having ir bands at 1770 and 1720 cm^{-1} and uv at 220 nm. Mass fragmentation data and signals in the pmr spectrum were in total agreement with those reported for inumakilactone B⁴. 4 was eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:4) and crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 276-78°. It formed a tetraacetate, m.p. 124-25°, as revealed in its pmr spectrum. Further, a signal corresponding to 1H at δ 4.85 (J 8 Hz) suggested it to be a glycoside. It was hydrolysed by HCl/acetic acid and the aglycone was identified as β -sitosterol and the sugar moiety as glucose. Hence, it was identified as the glucoside of β -sitosterol⁵.

The dried leaves (3 kg) were extracted with ethanol, and the concentrated extract was chromatographed on silica gel and the column eluted with benzene followed by increasingly polar mixtures of benzene-ethyl acetate. This resulted in the isolation of amentoflavone 7,7',4',4'''-tetramethyl ether (5), haveaflavone (6), amentoflavone 7',4'''-dimethyl ether (7), and amentoflavone (8). 5 was eluted from the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (19:1) and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 273-74°. It was characterised as a flavonoid on the basis of colour reactions. Methylation and acetylation of 5 led to the formation of hexamethyl ether and tetramethoxydiacetate derivatives of amentoflavone respectively. Pmr spectra of its derivatives, mass spectral data and comparison of 5 with authentic sample confirmed its identity as amentoflavone 7,7',4',4'''-tetramethyl ether^{6,7}. 6 was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, m.p. 312°; λ_{max} 270 and 330 nm; ν_{max} 1670 cm^{-1} ; gave positive colour tests for flavonoids. It was identified as haveaflavone on the basis of pmr spectral data of the acetate of 6 and by comparison of the methyl ether of 6 with a sample of amentoflavone hexamethyl ether⁸. 7 was crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 224°. Examination of the methylated product, m.p. 230°, and the pmr spectrum of its acetate led to its identification as amentoflavone 7',4'''-dimethyl ether⁹. 8 on methylation yielded amentoflavone hexamethyl ether, m.p. 227°, and on acetylation yielded hexaacetate of amentoflavone, m.p. 240-42°. 8 was therefore identified as amentoflavone¹⁰.

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Fatty Acid Composition of Rayan Seed Oil

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MIMUSOPS hexandra Linn. (Rayan), a plant belonging to sapotaceae family, bears sweet edible fruit known as 'Khirani' in Hindi. The bark of the plant is used in fever and as a general tonic¹. The characteristics and fatty acid composition have been studied earlier using older techniques². We report here the characteristics and fatty acid composition of the seed oil of Rayan from Madhya Pradesh using glc technique for the first time.

Experimental

The seeds of *M. hexandra* were crushed and extracted with light petroleum ether to yield a pale yellow oil with a faint odour. The characteristics of the oil determined by standard methods³ are given in the Table 1. The oil was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and the unsaponifiable matter was separated. The mixed fatty acids extracted with diethyl ether were converted to their methyl esters by refluxing with anhydrous methanol containing concentrated sulphuric acid⁴.

Tlc and argentation TLC (12.5% aqueous AgNO₃) of fatty acids and methyl esters were carried out on silica gel G. Glc of methyl esters was carried out in a CIC Baroda gas chromatograph equipped with flame ionisation detector and dual columns packed with 10% DEGS on Chromosorb (80-100 mesh) using nitrogen as carrier gas. The injection port, columns and flame ionisation detector block

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF RAYAN SEED OIL

Yield of oil (%)	24.0
Refractive index (at 30°)	1.4650
Saponification value	181
Iodine value	69
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	1.876
Fatty acids (%) :	
Myristic	0.25
Palmitic	20.86
Stearic	9.98
Oleic	52.66
Linoleic	16.85

were maintained at temperature 280, 180 and 180° respectively. Identification of the methyl esters was done using standard samples.

Results and Discussion

The characteristics and fatty acid composition of Rayan seed oil from Madhya Pradesh, being reported for the first time, are given in Table 1. It contains a high percentage of light coloured oil low in unsaponifiable content and is non-drying. Myristic acid (0.25%) is found in this variety and is reported for the first time. The oil is fairly stable and can be used for edible and other purposes after proper treatment.

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6',7'-Epoxyauraptene - A Coumarin from *Aegle marmelos*

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PREVIOUSLY we reported the structure of marmelide¹, a furanocoumarin from *Aegle marmelos*. Recent investigation of its root reveals the presence of another coumarin, 6',7'-epoxyauraptene (1).